

Measurement of Hydrogen Ion Activity by Clay Membrane Electrodes

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The glass electrode for pH measurement takes advantage of the fact that a special kind of soft glass out of which glass electrodes are made has the remarkable property of registering activity of H^+ -ions, but no anions and almost no other cations. The glass electrode is thus said to be specified towards H^+ .

Marshall and his associates¹ have devised non-specific or partially specific membrane electrodes for cations in general. They were made from preheated clay films. This means that all kind of cations are going to register more or less their activities on these electrodes. These membranes probably function in the same general manner as the glass electrode but with inferior specificity and over a more restricted range of concentrations in so far as H^+ -ions are concerned.

Fig. 1

Marshall further observed (*loc. cit.*) that the Nernst equation was not obeyed by the clay membrane electrodes when HCl solutions were employed; the liquid junction potential owing to the predominantly high conductance of H^+ -ions in comparison to Cl^- ions was perhaps responsible for this discrepancy.

The specificity of membrane electrodes may be conveniently expressed by "mobility ratio" which can be calculated from the e.m.f. observed between solutions of two cations of known activities on the two sides of a membrane (Marshall, *loc. cit.*). A high mobility ratio means that within a definite concentration range the membrane may be considered specific with respect to one of the cations. The reasons for the development of such

specificity are, however, not clear except that temperature of preheating may have some influence, besides the nature of the clay mineral used for the preparation of the membranes.

Cationic activity measurements, excluding those of H^+ -ions, could be successfully made by means of clay membrane electrodes even though the specificity was not appreciably high^{2,3}.

Some investigations were undertaken to prepare membranes from different clays isolated from soils, by preheating them to various temperatures. The development of specificity, if any, was then noted by calculating mobility ratios as stated above. In course of this work some of the membranes showed better promise in so far as measurement of H^+ ion activity was concerned and deserved a closer study, of which the following is a brief account.

EXPERIMENTAL

Clay membrane electrodes were prepared by the usual procedure² from $< 0.2\mu$ fractions of clay, isolated from a commercial source of Saurashtra bentonite and from a Jabalpur soil both from Madhya Pradesh. The Saurashtra clay was used in the H-form whereas the Jabalpur clay was in the Mg-form. The membranes from Saurashtra clay were heated for 48 hrs. in a muffle furnace at $480^\circ \pm 10^\circ$ and those from Jabalpur clay at $550^\circ \pm 10^\circ$. Selected pieces were then fixed to pyrex tubes with Piccin wax, and soaked in 0.1 N HCl solution for about two days, after which they were tested for asymmetry by placing the same HCl solution on the two sides of the electrodes and measuring e.m.f. between two calomel electrodes.

Solutions of HCl were prepared so as to have pH values ranging from 2.0 to 5.8 and their pH values were measured by means of the glass electrode pH meter. The same solutions were then used for measurements with the clay membrane electrodes in order to test their performance.

A similar set of solutions was prepared by taking acetic acid instead of HCl. Buffer solutions having low ionic concentrations ($< 0.01 N$) were also used for the purpose of pH measurement.

The procedure for pH measurement consisted in placing a solution of known pH (as measured by glass electrode) on one side of the clay membrane electrode and another, also of known pH , on the other side, care being taken to see that the two solutions do not differ by more than one unit of pH .

The results of the above measurements are given in Table I which show that some of the clay membrane electrodes perform fairly satisfactorily in the pH interval 2.15 to 5.8. The observed e.m.f. values refer to individual measurements with different membrane electrodes. The range of validity of the Nernst equation is clearly narrower than what has been found for such clay membrane electrodes in the case of metallic cations. The measured

2. D. K. Mitra, (1954). D.Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University.

3. S. K. Basu, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, 3, 65.

TABLE 1A

Saurashtra Bentonite

HCl solution was taken for pH measurements

Glass electrode pH	E.m.f. (mv) of	
	Theo.	Obs. (mean)
1. 2.9/2.15	44.3	44±2 (6*)
2. 2.9/2.4	29.5	30±1 (6*)
3. 3.15/2.2	56.1	56±1 (7*)
4. 3.95/3.05	53.1	52±1 (8*)
5. 4.1/3.3	47.2	46±1 (3*)
6. 4.7/3.95	44.3	44±2 (4*)
7. 4.9/3.9	59.0	57±1 (5*)
8. 5.8/5.1	41.3	41±1 (7*)

TABLE 1B

Jabalpur—Clay Membrane

Glass electrode pH	E.m.f. (mv) of	
	Theo.	Obs. (mean)
1. 3.05/2.2	50.1	50±1 (3*)
2. 4.0/3.05	56.9	55±2 (3*)
3. 4.65/4.2	26.6	24±1 (3*)

e.m.f.'s with buffer solutions on the two sides of the membrane electrodes (Saurashtra) are similarly compared in Table 2. It will be seen from the results that the electrodes do fairly well in the narrow range studied.

TABLE 2

E.m.f. measurements using buffer solutions

Buffer solution	Glass electrode pH	E.m.f. (mv) of combination			
		A/B		B/C	
		Theo.	Obs. (mean)	Theo.	Obs. (mean)
A. Pot. Hyd. phthalate (0.04M)	3.9	14.7	15±0.5 (6*)	36.4	37±2 (5*)
B. Pot. Hyd. phosphate (0.04M)	4.1		15±0.5 (2*)		
C. NaOAc-HOAc (0.01M)	4.7				

* The numbers within the brackets denote the number of observations.

Measurements were extended to high pH with acetate buffers. This was actually obtained by adding NaOH to an acetic acid solution. The inside of the membrane electrode contained acetic acid of known pH. Table 3 gives a comparison of the clay membrane

TABLE 3

Membrane Electrode	Glass Electrode
3.75	3.65
3.74	3.75
3.94	3.85
4.03	3.90
4.11	4.00
4.14	4.05
4.19	4.17
4.22	4.22
4.24	4.25
4.33	4.35
4.43	4.45
4.41	4.50
4.43	4.55
4.82	4.90
4.96	4.95
5.06	5.00
5.07	5.05
5.06	5.15
5.11	5.25
5.13	5.35
5.27	5.50
5.29	5.65
5.35	5.90
5.36	6.30
5.37	8.10
5.38	8.90
5.42	9.20

electrode with glass electrode pH values. The results clearly indicate that pH measurements by membrane electrode above pH 5.1 is not reliable. Beyond 9.0, the e.m.f. values were highly erratic and no stable values could be measured.

Electrodes were then selected for carrying out acid-base titration by taking a solution of suitable pH in the inside and the solution to be titrated on the out side. It will be seen by comparing with the glass-electrode titration curve that the one using the clay membrane electrode is almost featureless and shows no definite inflexion point. $NaCl$ that is formed in course of titration seems to influence, particularly towards the end of neutralisation, the shape of the curves as the clay membranes are likely to become sensitive towards increasing concentration of Na^+ ions as well. In fact, the addition of $NaCl$ from outside showed a decrease in measured pH . Obviously an electrode with a greater specificity for H^+ ions is required for more reliable pH measurement and acid-base titrations.

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